

Title: Successful Business with Machine Learning (Machine Learning in the business context).

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INTRODUCTION:

According to the experts from DeepMind, the Machine Learning market value is about 450 billion dollars in 2017 and will grow up to 30 trillion dollars before 2030. According to Economic Policy Institute, companies that use Machine Learning are frequently being acquired for billions of dollars. People, who are working with these technologies, are in the TOP 5% of people with the highest salaries. During this presentation I will talk about Successful Business with Machine Learning and how it can help you be the hero in your own business.

AIM:

To show Machine Learning in the business context based on case studies and research.

KEYWORDS:

Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Business

BIOGRAPHY:

Chief Executive Officer at Lonsley - a Machine Learning software house. While working for Women in Technology and Women Techmakers Krakow, she has created Tech Leaders - a mentoring programme for women in IT - a nationwide platform for the exchange of knowledge - aimed to support women who want to start their own businesses/startups and those who want to develop their careers as a successful employee. She is organising amazing events that support entrepreneurship and innovation.